

Prophylaxis for the Prevention of Crime Among Minors

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Abstract: In this article, the prevention of crime among minors, as well as the prevention of delinquency among minors, the identification and elimination of the causes of criminal behavior of adolescents, and the implementation of complex work on the basis of humanitarian approach are considered.

Key words: juveniles, prevention, crime and delinquency, family, rule of law, humanitarian, departmental services and institutions.

In our country, which has chosen the path of building a democratic legal state and a strong civil society, the protection of human rights and freedoms is enshrined in our national legislation. The large-scale work being carried out in the field of ensuring the rule of law, improving the legal culture of the population, and protecting the rights and interests of the young generation serves this noble purpose. In this regard, the creation of favorable conditions for the physical, mental and spiritual development of the growing young generation is one of the distinctive features of the strong social policy implemented in our country.

Prevention and fight against crimes committed by minors is one of the main directions of strong social policy implemented in our country. Juvenile delinquency as an independent object of criminological research is a component of the structure of general crime and has its own characteristics, which include: more negative and intensive growth dynamics compared to general crime, most crimes are committed by adults complicity in crimes; high percentage of mercenary and mercenary-violent crimes, high latency, increased aggression and brutality, group nature of crimes, etc.

In this regard, the Criminal Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is also of particular importance. Although the current Criminal Code contains certain provisions regarding the criminal liability of minors, it primarily provides for the protection of minors who commit crimes by the law through the principles of humanity, justice, and legality. The importance of the criminal law in this regard in protecting the future generation from criminal attacks and preventing juvenile delinquency is indisputable.

According to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the responsibility of minors has its own characteristics. The responsibility of minors is strengthened in articles 85-90 of the sixth section of the Criminal Code. The sixth chapter of the Code is called "Characteristics of the responsibility of minors" and consists of the chapters "Punishment and its imposition", "Release from responsibility and punishment". At the same time, the provisions of the general part of the Criminal Code are followed in the application of the provisions on the responsibility of minors, the imposition of punishment, exemption from responsibility and punishment, together with the above.

It is known that the analysis of the causal factors of the delinquent behavior of minors for many decades has always been the focus of interest of domestic and foreign researchers in various fields

of scientific knowledge: law, psychiatry, social sciences, medicine, pedagogy, etc. came Modern knowledge of behavioral disorders allows us to conclude that they are complex forms of social behavior of a person determined by a system of interrelated factors.

It should be noted that juvenile crime has a number of specific features that distinguish it from adult crime. First, the characteristics of this age: adolescence is always interpreted as a period of transition, critical. Adolescence is, first of all, a person's puberty, characterized by a person's hyperactivity in all areas. At the beginning of this period, a teenager begins to realize that he belongs to a certain gender, is interested in representatives of the other gender, and the first signs of sexual desire appear. Socially, the adolescent stage is a continuation of primary socialization. Almost all teenagers of this age are schoolchildren dependent on their parents and the state. The social status of a teenager is not much different from that of a child. The only difference is that a teenager has a sense of adulthood, a constant desire to present himself as an adult, to be reckoned with, and to respect his opinion. A teenager also learns external attributes of adult behavior: dressing, speaking; starts smoking, drinking alcohol, etc.

The next characteristic of the transitional period is severe mental retardation. Difficulties in life, especially in the period of self-assertion, the humiliation of dignity, because of these circumstances, despair often leads a young person to a dead end, and often his problems can only be solved by leaving life. leads to the idea that. The suicide statistics of teenagers and young adults are very alarming. In the list of causes of death for this age group, suicide ranks third after tuberculosis and injuries, and their number continues to grow. In nine out of ten cases, juvenile suicide attempts are not a desire to commit suicide, but a desire to attract attention, to call for help.

Also, crimes are committed by minors, usually on the street, in the circle of peers. Minors are distinguished by a great desire for group forms of recreation together. It is also typical of teenagers with deviant behavior who create their own groups. The main reasons why some teenagers and young people go to the path of crime are not the difficulties and shortcomings of education in themselves, but their immoral views, habits of the social environment (microenvironment), and direct transmission by imitation of their behavior. . "fake heroes" of foreign films. Thus, juvenile delinquency is the result of low social culture, moral bad behavior of the persons who committed them. Cultural and moral deformation of a certain person often occurs as a result of the negative influence of the microenvironment (family, peer group).

Most of the minors who commit crimes are drunkenness and alcoholism of their parents, brutality, regular violation of the rules of social behavior, committing crimes by them forms a criminogenic tendency in teenagers. Elimination of crimes should be carried out systematically, taking into account the management of social processes, and should be considered as an important social task of state importance.

The problem of juvenile delinquency cannot be ignored. Preventive measures in this area are an indispensable attribute of modern society. The concept of "prevention", which broadly means the prevention of any unpleasant events, has been around since the 1970s. began to be filled with legal content. According to A. Sattorova, the prevention of crimes means the activity of eliminating the causes and conditions of committing a crime by a person who has not yet shown criminal intent, but his behavior indicates a high probability of his becoming a criminal act. Crime prevention is also considered as a special type of social practice that ensures the change of social relations, as a result of which the conditions (causes, factors) contributing to deviant behavior are eliminated or neutralized.

Solving the problem of prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors should be based on the understanding of the social importance of the problem, in the center of which is the personality of the child, his future.

General and special preventive measures should be distinguished in the general system of state measures to prevent deviant behavior of minors. General prevention includes the creation of favorable socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-pedagogical conditions, which will help:

- performing reproductive functions of families, raising physically and socially healthy children;
- full implementation of educational functions, physically and socially healthy children;
- to fully implement the educational functions of all types of general education institutions, to ensure the development of children's abilities and positive interests, to organize their employment with useful activities outside of school hours.

The modern system of prevention of neglect is implemented by various departmental services and institutions. One of the most important tasks of public administration is the clear division of functions and spheres of preventive influence of various units. For example, in order to effectively organize the activities of the Parliament in the field of working with young people, recently the Commission on Youth Issues of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established and started its work. To create suitable conditions for young people, especially those who are not organized, not employed, and do not have a specific occupation, to ensure their employment, to develop their business skills, and to involve them in entrepreneurial activities. One of the main tasks of this commission was to make proposals for the introduction of effective mechanisms for the prevention of crime and delinquency among young people.

At the same time, issues related to the prevention of crime and offenses among young people, protecting them from the influence of various ideological threats and foreign ideas, meaningful spending of free time, and ensuring youth employment are covered. For example, issues such as regulation of internet clubs, the need to limit their activity after 10 pm are included. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness and responsibility of the state agencies responsible for this work, self-government bodies, public organizations, commissions dealing with minors.

Also, at the initiative of the President, Thursday of every week in our country is designated as the prevention day for the prevention of delinquency and crime. was an important direction in establishing

Law enforcement bodies, families, educational institutions and the general public are responsible for preventing delinquency and criminality of minors, participating in the spiritual, moral, legal, aesthetic, physical, and labor education of minors in the regions, forming a healthy lifestyle in them. tasks of assistance, social-pedagogical rehabilitation and adaptation of minors returning from penal institutions were assigned. Thus, it is possible to solve this problem only with the close cooperation of the bodies and institutions that implement the prevention of lack of control and offenses among minors.

In conclusion, various public and state organizations are responsible for raising and educating young people as healthy and perfect people, creating all the conditions for them to engage in sports and physical education, and organizing libraries so that they can use their free time effectively. If we work effectively in cooperation with the representatives and neighborhood activists, our well-educated, highly motivated youth will spare no effort and potential for the development of the life of the country and our people in the near and long term. Systematic reforms in the prevention of crimes in our country serve to ensure the peace and tranquility of our people.

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